

L. hexandra, *C. compressus*, *Cyperus rotundus*, and *C. iria* consistently harbored *P. oryzae*.

To study pathogenicity on rice, we inoculated potted seedlings of highly susceptible variety HR12 and popular variety KD2-6-3 at the 3- to 4-leaf stage with different isolates of *P. oryzae*. All isolates produced blast symptoms on HR12. The isolate from *C. compressus* failed to infect KD2-6-3 (see table). □

Diseases of deepwater rice in Jorhat District, Assam, India

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We surveyed 20 fields at different sites over some 6,000 ha of deepwater rice along the Brahmaputra River during rice flowering to ripening stages Oct-Dec 1987.

A general impression of disease incidence was obtained first, by walking across each sample field. A wooden quadrat 50 × 50 cm was placed at random along the field diagonal and the panicles infected with blast (BI) among those enclosed by a quadrat counted. Ten quadrat counts were made in each field. Other diseases were recorded similarly. For ufra, the top 30 cm portions of infested stems were collected to extract the stem nematode and to count nematodes per stem.

Ufra caused by *Ditylenchus angustus* was found at 15 sites. The disease appeared in distinct patches. On the average, 55% of the stems were infected in an ufra patch. The most common symptoms were nonemergence of panicles and half-emerged panicles.

In the most severe form of ufra, a rudimentary, skeletal panicle protruded from the boot (Fig. 1). The highest count of nematodes per stem was 7,500. Some ratoon tillers in ufra patches had chlorotic ufra symptoms: chlorosis of the youngest leaf at the neck region with brown stains on the midrib (Fig. 2). This symptom resembles a mite attack.

1. Most severe symptom of ufra — twisted ear protruding (arrow) from the boot. Assam, India, 1987.

Dominant deepwater varieties Amanabao and Rangabao were highly susceptible to ufra.

Neck BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* was the second most important disease. On the average, 25% of the panicles in 10 infested fields were infected. Ratoon tillers from basal stem nodes were infected with leaf BI; typical BI spots also were observed on the flag leaves. Nodal BI was common in several fields.

2. Chlorotic ufra symptom in ratoon tillers. Assam, India, 1987.

Amanabao and Rangabao were susceptible to neck BI.

Other diseases found were sheath rot (less than 1% stems infected), bacterial blight (5% leaf area infected), brown spot (less than 5% leaf area infected), false smut (1% panicles infected), and kernel smut (1% panicles infected). □

Host plants of ragged stunt virus (RSV)

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We inoculated young seedlings of 2 *Oryza* spp. and 15 weed species separately with 20 RSV-viruliferous brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* each. Inoculated plants were indexed by ELISA 30 d after inoculation. Extracts of plants with absorbance at 405 nm